

Effects of Early Childhood Education Practices on Pupils' Performance in Primary Schools of Rwanda

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Abstract: The research assessed the effect of early childhood education practices on pupils' performance in primary schools of Rwanda, a case of Gasabo district. Given that the practices of schools in Gasabo-Rwanda is apparently not set to provide effective support to the acquisition of the adequate performance for the primary pupils, the researcher's attention was attracted and aimed at finding out the effect of early childhood education practices on pupils' performance in primary schools of Rwanda. The target population of this research was 5646 population, from which a sample size of 96 respondents were chosen as the participants either 8 educational leaders (head teachers) or 16 teachers or 72 parents chosen from four schools of 4 Gasabo District and they were sampled using a simple random and purposive sampling techniques. In this research, two questionnaires were administered and collected from parents and teachers while the interviews were administered to head teachers. The findings indicated that even through there were many practice that boosted the early childhood effective learning there are also a number of practices of school stakeholders that weaken the development of pre-primary adequate competences among others teacher recruitment of qualified teachers, lack of educational leaders monitoring of teaching in pre-primary classes, lack of professional development for Early Childhood Education teachers, lack of material delivery and others equipment for pre-primary and lack of awareness about the requirements for Early Childhood Education children including inappropriate nutrition. Recommendations were addressed to the Ministry of Education and affiliated institutions requesting further investment in pre-primary school management by empowering school leaders and raising their awareness on all aspects of Early Childhood Education to facilitate their support towards Early Childhood Education teachers who are the primary agents for the development of early childhood education pupils' competences.

Keywords: Early Childhood Education (ECE), Primary education.

1. BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Early childhood development (ECD) is a critical period that continues to impact human health and productivity throughout the lifetime. Failing to provide policies and programs that support optimal developmental attainment when such services are financially and logistically feasible can result in negative population health, education, and economic consequences that might otherwise be avoided.

Gestwicki and Bertrand (2011) claim that early childhood educators have to create a specific environment to develop teamwork. First, principals or caregivers need to be aware of the latest findings in the field to be able to exploit new techniques and strategies in their nurseries, centers, etc. Second, caregivers should also be able to encourage their staff to develop new ways and approaches and come up with innovative ideas.

In Indonesia, in agreement with the circumstances required in Specialized Direction for Foundation of Kindergarten (2015) states that, (Directorate of Early Childhood Education, Ministry of Education of Republic of Indonesia, 2015: 43). The instructing and learning apply week by week and day by day lesson plans, which are carried out through exterior and interior classroom exercises. It appeared that the educator and understudies perform three sets of forms specifically presentation, the center exercises, and closing movement. Hence, it was concluded that the preschool program fulfilled instructing and learning, and process. In Indonesia, in understanding the circumstances required in Specialized Direction for Foundation of Kindergarten (2015) states that, in case the instructing and learning handle takes 6 days, the term of considering barring breaks.

In African countries like Botswana, an examination of the early childhood care and instruction approach and programming that was commissioned by UNESCO and the Service of Instruction in 2009 distinguished a number of boundaries and services within the ECCE approach including inadequate instructors particularly in community schools and a deficiency of professionally prepared workforce to uphold the arrangement. This approach unfavorably influences the quality of pre-school education. For example, there's a need for the capacity to guarantee that pre-schools comply with existing measures.

Early Childhood Care and Advancement (ECCD) states that in 2000, there were 257 nursery schools in Rwanda of which as it were two were government-owned. These pre-schools catered for 18,399 children out of approximately 2 million preschool-aged children. Typically fair beneath 1%. These schools are overseen by 527 instructors, the lion's share of who have gotten as it were in-service preparing. In line with other angles of its command, the part of MINEDUC will be at the level of policymaking and supervision. The government did not back preschool instruction, but or maybe advertised specialized bolster and arranged to give motivations to the private segment to supply such administrations. To educate children social and enthusiastic aptitudes, most instructors utilize one of two approaches to classroom administration or a combination of them both: 1) proactively instructing children how to oversee their connections and situations by educating social and enthusiastic aptitudes, or 2) disheartening children's misbehavior with results and disciplines such as "time out" or stoplight (ruddy light, green light) systems. For the teacher to realize these classroom practices is the key to providing support to teachers. According to Haynes (2010), preschool learning must be well prepared, considering learning is a complex activity. He also highlighted that there are three steps in the learning process. The first step is planning and preparation, the second step is the activities in the classroom including classroom management, teaching, and learning, and the third step is reporting and evaluation (the activity that takes place after the learning process of assessment, with related activities such as feedback and evaluation).

1.1 Problem Statement

Ideally, the Government of Rwanda intends to improve the capacity for planning, management, and administration of education (ESSP, 2017). This government perspective aims to improve the education leaders' performance in planning education-related activities including conducting effective supervision and inspection of the education activities, planning, and managing educators' professional development, establishing a conducive working environment, conducting worked related appraisals, dispatching physical and qualified human resources accordingly and help all the education stakeholders to implement their activities right in the right place and time. The statistics showed that 65% students who attend nursery levels before they start primary levels perform well since they got enough skills used in the pre-primary levels.

MIGEPROF in its ECD policy and strategic framework states five strategic focus areas namely parenting education support, school readiness, and transition, which are the main areas of concern in this study whereby the early childhood, would focus. Parenting education support starts from parents who are key to Early Childhood Education as the primary providers of the basic needs of the young children such as food, porridge, and care. Currently, the school leaders in public schools are not holding the responsibility to care about the ECE that are located in the schools they lead despite the presence of the policy and framework. The current early childhood schools lack skills and experience in the management of ECE, they lack performance to support ECE teachers in terms of teaching approaches and professional development. Consequently, the ECE classes are being managed by teachers who often are not even trained to teach in Early Childhood Education. The school leaders are not empowered in the management of ECE programs which are far different from primary and secondary education. If this situation continues, the ECE programs will not reach the intended outcome and their implementation will be doubtful and consequences will fall upon the future generation of the country that would not benefit from the proper early education as planned in various policies about ECD.

1.2 General objective

The general objective of the study is to assess the effects of early childhood education practices on pupils' performance in primary schools of Gasabo District- Rwanda.

1.3 Specific objectives

i. To identify early childhood education practices related to pupils' performance in primary schools in Rwanda;

1.4 Research Questions

i. To what extent early childhood education practices are related to pupils' performance in primary schools in Rwanda?

1.5 Significance of the Study

This study has given valuable experience due to the following points: The study has provided adequate information about the effects of early childhood practices on pupil's performance in primary schools of Rwanda, Specifically, the study has provided information on how ECE practices affect pupils' performance of primary in Gasabo District. Furthermore, the findings of this study will be beneficial to the researcher herself due to her more understanding of how ECE practices can have a significant impact in pupils' performance of pre-primaries.

In addition, this study will give a contribution to the country of Rwanda about exploration to the early childhood education practices and its effect on pupils' performance in primary schools of Rwanda. Not only students who will have good scores and gain competences but also will be beneficial to the district leaders such as DDEs, DEOs in charge of primaries and SEIs, to know where to put much effort for effective and sustainability of primary schools management in Rwanda

1.6 Limitation of the Study

Some journal articles and books were needed and may have to be purchased online; this may cost ;2a lot of money. Thus, the researcher utilized se downloadable free journals for reading offline. The researcher could also face a barrier on the unavailability of respondents where some of the selected respondents might not be available during the period of data collection du tot other conflicting responsibilities, the researcher got appointment depending on the availability of the respondents and reach out to them.

1.7 Geographical scope

This study was conducted in sampled public and private primary schools of Gasabo District which is located in the Kigali City "the capital City of Rwanda"; the district is made of 15 sectors through which the researcher 1 selected 4 schools for the study.

1.8 Time Scope

In terms of time, this research project was carried out to investigate the effect of early childhood education practices on pupils' performance in primary schools of Rwanda. Thus, the research project was carried out by the researcher from October, 2023 to April, 2024.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In this section, the researcher discussed the scholars works related to the topic and the effect of early childhood in Gasabo District was used as a case study. Therefore the researcher deeply instead reviewed theoretical review related to the early childhood education practices as independent variables and pupils' performance in primary schools as dependent variables and interpreting my topic related to the empirical review of other researchers and making conclusions about this chapter and conceptual framework of the study.

2.1 Empirical Literature

Where various definitions of authority exist, one that shows up to capture exceptionally well the central meaning of authority is given by Robbins, Millet, Caccioppe, & Waters (2015) who say administration is "the capacity to impact others towards the accomplishment of objectives that contribute to a beneficial purpose. In ECE, authority is imperative since it is mindful for calling, for a commitment and enthusiasm from each part of the ECE setting to form a commitment which

results in a positive contrast within the lives of the children within the ECE setting and to assist lay the establishment which is able offer assistance them to create into beneficial citizens who will be able to live and work beneficially in progressively powerfully complex societies.

2.1.1 Identifying Early Childhood Education Practices Related to Pupils

McCrea (2015) bargains with this point exceptionally well when she proposes that authority in an ECE setting is almost bringing enhancement through affecting individuals, in places where ECE takes place, and locks in and empowering the conduct of proficient and moral practices.

As many ECE competences are identified via use of plays and games, Betty S. G. Teo (2014) cited that the 'instructor is the key center to the play curriculum' (Van Hoorn, Nourot, Scales and Alward, 2013). Betty S. G. Teo (2014) emphasized that the reason is that educators need to utilize their data to 'carefully facilitate the stream from unconstrained play, to more subject-oriented instruction, and back to play.' Van Hoorn et al clarify that such play instructive modules stream must take the lesson and the children's individual needs and enhancement into thought. Van Hoorn et al advocate that a play-centered instructive program requires educators to have the qualities of being peppy, unconstrained, creative, clever, and interpretive. Van Hoorn et al portray play-centered instructive programs as a 'teacher facilitated rather than educator controlled instructive programs. It isn't a 'laissez-faire play instructive program where no one observes or intervenes. The proprietor of the childcare centers needs to propel instructors to be child inviting. Instructors ought to develop paternalistic authority, in this manner seeing the children as their claim, snuggling them, and energizing them to have an adoration for ponders. Instructors got to present to children the soul of reasonable play, and sharing, since not much mental work is included but basically the utilization of the play-way strategy in educating and learning. This will offer assistance to the child to be law based afterward a long time.

Teachers' got to assign greater and shrewder children as screens to donate them opportunities for preliminary administration. Instructors of children centers have to be utilizing a dictatorial leadership style in handling the children in some cases in order to preserve a few forms of disciplinary information such as, don't urinate within the lesson, or don't eat within the lesson some time recently during break period. Instructors of kindergarten schools can moreover apply the Laissez-faire demeanor towards the conclusion of the school area by permitting more or guided flexibility to students to perform errands on their claim. Students seem to learn from involvement, disclosure, and imagination whereas on their claim.

2.1.2 Early childhood education practices related to pupils' performance

ECE is considered to be of most extraordinary significance. This is often regularly realized by all the people of the community, independent of their establishments and occupations. The essential three a long time of the life of the individual are considered to be crucial. At this organization, the child makes the affiliations to lead to movement. When they will be careful of distinctive strategies in terms of child enhancement, they will be able to render a solid commitment. Gatekeepers are the ones, who are committed and competent to a major degree for the specialist advancement and progression of their children.

Until the age of three, children are close to their mothers and depend upon them for utilization of all works out and capacities. When children reach the age of four, they begin to realize that outside their residence there's a world, which they have to get familiar with. ECE makes a contrast with the understudies to make their mental capacity and make strides their capacities and capacities. The social necessities of an individual begin to extend as he creates. ECE is critical since it makes a course of action of data and information that focuses on the common change of the individual. This run has bought into nearness the works of various researchers, investigators, educationists and money related examiners. Individuals and organizations, who have made sharp captivation and enthusiasm in this locale, have worked towards headway.

The issues relating to financial development and proficiency have been a matter of concern and ECE may be a concern, since it renders a basic commitment towards the headway of future citizens, (Calman & Whelan, 2015). The destinations of ECE have been communicated as follows: (Currie, 2011). Headway of the child is considered to be one of the major targets of ECE and it centers upon three locales. These join cognitive aptitudes, school accessibility and social and enthusiastic enhancement.

Understudies got to be teaching how to work out more self-control. Out of different sorts of behavioral characteristics, a couple are considered to be positive, whereas some are negative. When the understudies are energetic, they may delineate certain behavioral characteristics, which may not be palatable interior the community or school or residential, such as yelling or crying, in this way, they have to be teaching how to remain calm and calm undoubtedly when they are experiencing troublesome circumstances (Graafweg, A. 2009).

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The researcher used cross-sectional and comparative research design in order to establish a relationship among/ between variables. The main purpose of this research is to discover the effects of primary practices on pupils' performance in primary education schools. The researcher collected qualitative data and quantitative data from respondents to be analyzed, and then the research is to investigate and compare the effects of primary practices and pupils' performance in pre-primaries education using qualitative and quantitative methods. The study is exploratory research because quantitative data which was primary school academic performance in percentage was collected and analyzed with the goal of considering or interpreting the qualitative data. The research design is cross-sectional and comparative in order to attempt to establish a relationship among/ between variables (Komp & Tromp, 2006).

3.1 Target and Sample Population

Same with primary pupils in schools of Gasabo District and they constituted at the same time the population for the study. According to the report of Gasabo district, the whole population comprised 5,646 people. As the study population was limited to school 64 leaders, 5431 parents of the students of primary and 151 teachers, that is the product that represented the primary school number in Gasabo district.

Table 1: Target population and sample size

Respondents	Number of employees	Sample design
Parents	5431	72
Teachers	151	16
School leaders/ educational officials	64	8
Total	5646	96

Source: Researcher (2024)

3.2 Sampling Technique

Simple random and purposive methods were used for this study. This entailed dividing the population into 2 mutually exclusive groups; in this case the various job cadres and random samples were drawn from each group. The researcher selected individuals from the sample size in Gasabo District. This saved time and cost of undertaking the study.

3.3 Primary data

As put forward by (Hagood, 2012) "if a person or agency that has published data were earlier collected or supervised the collection of data, the publication was called a primary source"; (Audrey, 2011), «primary sources come straight from people or workers you are researching and therefore the most direct kind of information that the researcher can collect». «That is the reason why primary data are firstly gathered by the researcher as a result of the researcher's investigation». In this research, the primary data were composed of information from questions (both qualitative and quantitative) of relevant staff on the effect of early childhood education practices on pupils' performance in primary schools of Rwanda with a case of Gasabo District.

3.3.1 Questionnaire

"The questionnaire will help the researcher as the main means of communication between researcher and respondents. Questionnaire included the series of questions about issues that were expected of the respondent information, where these types of questions were distributed by the researcher among respondents in order to collect the written and quantitative data (information) related to the topic".

3.3.2 Interview

According to Krlinger (2017), meet could be a conversation from which the analysts attempt to induce data to the interviewees. "Subjective questions were inquired in connection with the investigate destinations and this makes a difference the researchers to get direct information from respondents; therefore, this technique allowed the researcher to collect information" related to the effect of early childhood education practices on pupils' performance in primary schools of Rwanda through oral communication with selected staff who are working with Gasabo District and the researcher approached respondents in order to see the development technique to be used.

3.4 Ethical considerations

Whereas conducting the think about, the analyst was watched and regarded different inquire about morals such as genuineness, objectivity, astuteness, openness, secrecy, social duty, non-discrimination, performance, human subjects' security. The analyst to begin with clarified the reason for the inquiry to respondents, regarded human respect and regarded the respondents' choice to participate/ not take part within the ponder. As it was educated assent was looked for and names of respondents were not uncovered within the dissertation. The researcher got an authorization letter from the university and then clearance letter from the Gasabo District before embarking on the field.

4. RESULTS

In this section the researcher presented data, interpreted and analyzed the information for from the different population respondents,

4.1 Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

The total number of the respondents was 151 made of 8 head- teachers, 16 teachers and 120 parents in pre-primary schools of Gasabo District.

Table 1: Distribution of the head teachers by their level of education

Level of education		Frequencies	Percentages
1.	Secondary	0	0
2.	Diploma	0	0
3.	Undergraduate	7	87
4.	Postgraduate	1	13
Total		8	100

Source: Field data (2024)

The table 2 shows the level of education of the head teachers. All 7 out of 8 which is equivalent to 87% respondents have undergraduate degrees from higher learning institutions of education. One of them, equivalent to 13%, has a postgraduate degree. The findings showed that to be a head teacher of a Complex School requires a qualification of at least bachelor's degree in education.

4.2 Presentation of the Findings

The presentation of the findings has focused on the specific objectives of the research which were to identify early childhood education management factors related to pupils' performance in pre-primary schools in Rwanda; to analyze pupils' performance requirements in pre-primary schools in Rwanda and finally to establish the effect of early childhood education on school management factors on pupils ' performance in pre-primary school in Rwanda.

4.2.1 Identify early childhood education practices related to pupils' performance

The findings based on the objective one were presented and discussed to answer the questions of the research questionnaires and the interview guide given to the head teachers and teachers as the educationalists and managers in the pre-primary schools.

According to the research information obtained from the respondents, the following were the data collected from the field: The head teachers' responses to the identification of early childhood performance; there were 8 respondents on the side of the head teachers, equivalent to 100%, and all of them were present during the data collection stage. 8 interview sets were conducted with the head teachers and the findings are shown in the following table 5.

Table 5: Head Teachers' responses to identification of early childhood education

Statements	Strongly disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly agree		Standard Deviation
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	
Gasabo district promoting ECE professionalism	0	0	4	50	2	25	2	25	0	0	0.66
Gasabo district is recruiting qualified ECE teachers and caregivers	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	25	6	75	0.61
Gasabo district ECE leaders monitor and assess ECE staff to assure implemented	1	13	3	37	3	37	1	13	0	0	0.68

Source: Data from field (2024)

For the identification of early childhood education management factors related to pupils' performance in pre-primary schools in Gasabo District, 4 out of 8 head teachers disagree that there is promotion of ECE professionalism in different areas of school leadership. Only two out of 8 agree that Gasabo District promotes ECE professionalism and the remaining two head teachers out of 8 have demonstrated neutrality on this question. Therefore, as the questionnaires were given to 8 head teachers of selected pre-primary schools of Gasabo district, and the findings showed that the majority of the respondents raised that the pre-primary pupils' competences are not dependent on the promotion of ECE professionalism in various areas of school leadership. The minority of the respondents affirmed that Gasabo district promotes ECE professionalism in leadership to support pre-primary.

The study showed that 6 out of 8 head teachers equivalent to 75% have strongly confirmed that Gasabo district is recruiting qualified ECE teachers and caregivers for pupils' development in all learning areas whereas 2 out of 8 equivalent to 25% agreed to this point. Therefore, identification of early childhood education management factors related to pupils' performance in pre-primary schools has shown that the recruitment of qualified teachers and caregivers for pupils' development in all learning areas is the only factor that is influencing the pupils' performance in Pre-primary in Gasabo District. The promotion of ECE professionalism and the monitoring and assessment of ECE staff to assure ECE curriculum is being implemented has not been done to influence the pupils' performance in pre-primary in Gasabo district.

Table 6: Teachers' responses to the identification of early childhood practices

Statements	Strongly disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly agree		Standard Deviation
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	
The teacher demonstrates an understanding of the importance plays	0	0	0	0	2	12	12	76	2	12	0.74
The teacher has sufficient teaching aids and all other teaching resources in the classroom	10	63	0	0	1	6	3	19	2	12	0.85
Each learning corner is equipped with sufficient and appropriate materials	0	0	11	69	1	6	4	25	0	0	0.71

Source: Data from field (2024)

For the identification of early childhood education practices related to pupils' performance in pre-primary schools in Gasabo District, 16 teachers provided their responses to the questions seeking to identify early childhood education management factors related to pupils' competences in pre-primary schools in Gasabo.

The number of 12 respondent teachers; equivalent to 76% agree that the teacher demonstrates an understanding of the importance of learning through play as one factor of developing pupils' competences in pre-primary. Two teachers out of 16 strongly agree to the point that the teacher demonstrates an understanding of the importance of learning through play. Only two out of 16 respondents have demonstrated that they were neutral to the fact that the teacher demonstrates an understanding of the importance of learning through play. However, 10 respondents out of 16 equivalent to 63% strongly disagree with the fact that teachers have sufficient teaching aids and all other teaching resources in the classroom to develop all skills ECE as one factor related to pupils' competences in pre-primary schools. Only 2 respondents out of 16 equivalent to 12% strongly agree that teacher has sufficient teaching aids and all other teaching resources in the classroom to develop all skills ECE and 3 out of 16 equivalent to 19% agree that teacher has sufficient teaching aids and all other teaching resources in the classroom to develop all skills ECE. The total respondents of 5 out of 16 equivalent to 31% who strongly agreed and agree that teacher has sufficient teaching aids and all other teaching resources in the classroom to develop all skills ECE, is far below the ones who strongly disagree equaled to 10 plus 1 who declared neutral and who altogether totalize 11 equivalent to 69% of the total respondents.

Again, 11 out of 16 respondents equivalent to 69% disagreed that each learning corner is equipped with sufficient and appropriate materials to help children in all learning and teaching activities. Only 4 out of 16 respondents equivalent to 25% agreed that Each learning corner is equipped with sufficient and appropriate materials to help children in all learning and teaching activities. This implies that, on the side of teachers, the factor of having sufficient teaching aids and all other teaching resources in the classroom to develop all skills ECE and having each learning corner equipped with sufficient and appropriate materials to help children in all learning and teaching activities have no influence on the development of pupils competences in pre-primary schools in Gasabo.

The parents' responses to the identification of early childhood education; the total of 72 questionnaires were distributed to parents and all 72 were returned. It means that the researcher received 100% of the questionnaires distributed to the parents.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study entitled: "Effect of early childhood education school management on pupils' competences in pre-primary schools of Rwanda, a case of Gasabo District. The research was comprehensively guided by the following discussed general objective "to examine the effect of early childhood education school management factors on pupils' competences in pre-primary schools of Rwanda and specific objective which was to identify early childhood education practices related to pupils' performance in pre-primary schools in Rwanda. The research was conducted in an investigative method which consisted of the provision of questionnaires and interview administration, all used to supplement the disclosed information.

5.1 Early Childhood Education Management Practices

The objective one, which was to identify early childhood education practices related to pupils' performance in pre-primary schools in Rwanda revealed that most of the factors affect the acquisition of the expected competences in ECE as the majority of the respondents either head teachers or teachers or parents are on the side that the current ECE school management factors are not fully favorable for the development of pupils' competences as indicated in the tables. 100% of the head teachers agree that recruitment of ECE teachers and caregivers is happening though they are not all qualified to teach in pre-primary but at least they are recruited to be on the government payroll compared to the long period ago where they were employed as volunteers. However 50% of the head teachers disagree that there is promotion of ECE professionalism in different areas of leadership. Moreover, 50% of the head teachers disagree that there is monitoring and assessment of ECE staff to ensure that the ECE curriculum is being implemented. On one side of teachers, 88% affirm that teacher demonstrates an understanding of the importance of learning through play on the other side 63% deny that teachers have sufficient teaching aids all other teaching resources in the classroom to develop all skills and 69% deny that each learning corner is equipped with sufficient and appropriate materials to help children in all learning and teaching activities. 83% of the parents respondents confirm that they have observed that teachers in ECE demonstrate

understanding of the impact of early learning in a person's long-life learning in addition 68% of the respondents also affirm that parents with children in the nursery section attend school general assembly meetings. However, 62% of the same respondents deny that parents from the nursery section provide needed materials to their children

5.2 Conclusions

The researcher concluded that there were deep gaps in the factors that would make the school management of ECE to effectively develop pupils' competences in pre-primary. Though recruitment of ECE teachers is done and appreciated but the recruited teachers are not qualified to teach ECE moreover there is lack of consistent monitoring of classroom activities because even the school leaders are not empowered in supervising ECE classes and there is lack of continuous professional development for ECE teachers since the school leaders, School Based Mentors and School Based Trainers are not empowered to support this field of pre-primary. It was also found out that teachers need to be equipped with skills to implement teaching and learning through play and there is a lack of teaching and learning materials. Parents are key role players for making the ECE appropriately provide required competences while they not only provide required school materials but also improve their understanding on the impact of pre-primary schooling for human kind life and attend school meetings to support the school leadership to make effective decisions. The stated factors work together to impact the pre-primary teaching and learning and missing one of them makes the process of achieving the appropriate ECE school management which hinder the acquisition of required competences.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings and the conclusions drawn from the conducted investigation, the researcher would recommend the ministry of education with its institutions in charge implementation of education policies, government institutions that oversee the family promotion and gender, districts, school leaders, teachers and parents that for the pre-primary to provide the expected competences teachers have to be equipped enough to handle all that matters for pre-primary.

The school leaders have to be empowered on every single detail of the pre-primary section to support both teachers and parents in terms of classroom observation, daily schedules, play-based teaching and learning and use of the pre-primary teaching and learning materials.

The school leaders are required to be playful with these young children and receive acquaintance on the learning styles that far differ from other levels of learning.

The researcher also recommended that the development of the teachers of ECE in TTCs given that the number of qualified candidates for teaching ECE is very small compared to the needed. TTCs should also produce teachers who are equipped with the ECE required skills on the ground since as the findings have shown; the teachers in place from TTCs are still struggling to adopt the designed curriculum, play-based approach and the daily schedule.

Furthermore, recommendations should go to parents whose children are at the age of pre-primary stage that they improve awareness of the needs of their children once sent to pre-primary, especially the appropriate nutrition that goes hand in hand with the teaching approach that is used in pre-primary.

The last but not least recommendations go to local government leaders to support the implementation of ECE and encourage local communities to send their children to pre-primary because a lot of benefits for young children are found in ECE.

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